

STUDIES IN SULPHONAMIDES—A NEW APPROACH. PART I

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Some sulphonamides of the general type

have been prepared and their properties described.

Amongst the sulphonamides sulphathiazole and sulphadiazine are the drugs of choice. Stetten and Fox (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1945, 161, 333) and Shive *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 69, 725) have established that these two sulphonamides interfere with the growth of bacteria, and 4-amino-5-carboxamido-imidazole (I) accumulates in the medium. Though it is well recognised that sulphonamides are bacteriostatic, it is not possible yet to draw a sharp line between a true bacteriostatic and a true bacteriocidal drug. Whether the imidazole (I) appears as a result of bacteriostatic or bacteriocidal nature, however small it may be, remains to be decided. However, it is obvious that these drugs act as antimetabolites to two essential metabolites, viz., *p*-aminobenzoic acid and 4-amino-5-carboxamido-imidazole.

From the point of view of metabolite-antimetabolite relationship, there is no similarity between the structures of sulphathiazole and sulphadiazine with (I), and it may be concluded that their antimetabolite action with respect to (I) may be of a low order.

It is therefore considered of interest to synthesise new sulphonamides with combination of groups which possibly could act as antimetabolites against PABA as well as against (I) to a greater measure than is the case with the present known drugs of the class.

After surveying the subject of metabolites, particularly reviews by Roblin (*Chem. Rev.*, 1946, 33, 255) and Wooley ("A Study of Antimetabolites", 1952, Chap. 10), it is considered worthwhile to synthesise compounds of the general structure (II), its ring-closed compound (IIA) and its corresponding sulphone (IIB). The work could be extended to compounds of the structures (III), (IV), (V) and (VI) and their corresponding ring-closed compounds and sulphones; $\text{R}^1, \text{R}^2, \text{R}^3, \text{R}^4$ being H or other groups.

Besides the chemotherapeutic point of view, there is a fundamental interest involved in studying the chemistry of the rings (IIA) and the corresponding ring systems of (III), (IV), (V) and (VI), which will be new.

In the present investigation sulphonamides of the general structure (II) have been synthesised according to the following schemes:

[R = H or Me ; R¹ = H or alkyl or thiazole or aryl group ; X = H or Cl]

EXPERIMENTAL

Formation of Amides.—A mixture of isatoic or 5-methylisatoic anhydride (1 M) (Bredt and Hof, *Ber.*, 1900, **33**, 27) and the particular amine (1 M) was heated on a water-bath for 2 hours and the compound crystallised from a suitable solvent. In case of the condensation with 2-amino-4-phenylthiazole, 2-amino-4-(*p*-chlorophenyl)-thiazole and 2-amino-4-methyl-5-carbomethoxythiazole, the reaction temperatures used were 140°-160°, 160°-170° and 155°-165° respectively and the time allowed was only one hour in case of compounds No. 5, 12 and 13 (Table I).

Formation of Sulphonamides.—The various listed sulphonamides (Table II) have been prepared by one of the following two general methods.

Method A.—*o*-Aminobenzamide or substituted benzamide (1 M) was dissolved in a requisite amount of dry ether, and pyridine (1 M) was added to it. *p*-Acetylamino-benzenesulphonyl chloride (1 M) was mixed with it with shaking and allowed to stay for a requisite interval of time. In case there was no separation, the reaction mixture was gently refluxed for sometime. Ether was then removed and the residue triturated with hot water, cooled, filtered at suction and the substance crystallised.

Method B.—*o*-Aminobenzamide or substituted benzamide (1 M) was mixed with pyridine (1 M), and *p*-acetylamino-benzenesulphonyl chloride (1 M) added and heated on a water-bath (or at 110-120° in some cases) for 2 hours. Pyridine hydrochloride was dissolved out with water as in method A and the residue was crystallised.

2-N⁴-Chloroacetylsulphanilamidobenzamide (VIII: R=R¹=H; X=Cl).—This was prepared by method A using 120 c.c. of dry ether, pyridine (0.6 c.c.) for 1 g. of the 2-aminobenzamide, followed by the addition of *p*-chloroacetylamino-benzenesulphonyl chloride (1.97 g.). The resulting solution was warmed for 15 minutes and kept at room temperature for 50 hours. The residue after distillation of ether was treated with water (20 c.c.), collected and crystallised from 60% ethanol in white needles, m.p. 193°, yield 1.68 g. (Found: N, 11.80. C₁₅H₁₄O₄N₄S requires N, 11.43 per cent).

2-N⁴-Diethylaminoacetylsulphanilamide.—To a solution of (VIII: R=R¹=H; X=Cl) (1 g.) in 15 c.c. of dry acetone was added diethylamine (2 M). After refluxing for one hour the solvent was distilled off and the residue washed with water (20 c.c.). The water-insoluble product was crystallised from ethanol in white needles, m.p. 200°, yield 0.45 g. (Found: N, 14.20. C₁₉H₂₁O₄N₄S requires N, 13.86 per cent).

TABLE I

Amides of structure

No.	Reactants. Anhydride.	Base	R ¹	Structure.	Product synthesised. Nomenclature.	Cryst. from.	M.P.	*Yield.	% Nitrogen. Found.	Calc.
1.	Isatoic	Ethanolamine	H	R ¹ = —CH ₂ CH ₂ OH	2-Amino-(hydroxyethyl)- benzamide.	Benzene	95°	0.80 g.	16.10	15.60
2.	Do	<i>o</i> -Anisidine	H	—C ₆ H ₄ OMe (<i>o</i>)	2-Aminobenz- <i>o</i> -anisidine.	66% EtOH	110°	2.06	11.50	11.57
3.	Do	2-Amino-4-(<i>p</i> -chlorophenyl)-thiazole	H		2-[2-Aminobenzamido]-4-(<i>p</i> -chlorophenyl)-thiazole.	EtOH	182°	1.95	12.50	12.74
4.	Do	2-Amino-4-methyl-5-carbethoxythiazole	H		2-[2-Aminobenzamido]-4-methyl-5-carbethoxy-thiazole.	Glacial acetic acid	138°	1.48	13.20	13.12
5.	Do	2-Amino-4-phenyl-thiazole	H		2-[2-Aminobenzamido]-4-phenylthiazole.	EtOH	150°	1.80	14.40	14.20

TABLE I (contd.)

No.	Reactants.		Structure.	Product synthesised.	Nomenclature.	Cryst. from.	M. P.	*Yield.	%Nitrogen.	
	Anhydride.	Base.							Found.	Calc.
6.	5-Methyl- isatoic	Aniline	R = Me R ₁ = Ph		2-Amino-5-methylbenzamide.	EtOH	162°	1.70 g.	12.10°	12.39
7.	Do	<i>o</i> -Toluidine	Me	-- <i>o</i> -tol.	2-Amino-5-methylbenzotoluidide.	Aq. EtOH	170°	1.07	11.40	11.66
8.	Do	<i>m</i> -Toluidine	Me	-- <i>m</i> -tol.	2-Amino-5-methylbenzotoluidide.	EtOH	148°	1.88	11.81	11.66
9.	Do	<i>p</i> -Toluidine	Me	-- <i>p</i> -tol.	2-Amino-5-methylbenzotoluidide.	"	183°	1.55	12.00	11.66
10.	Do	<i>o</i> -Anisidine	Me	--C ₆ H ₄ OMe(<i>o</i>)	2-Amino-5-methylbenzotoluidide.	Aq. EtOH	98°	2.14	11.50	10.94
11.	Do	<i>p</i> -Anisidine	Me	--C ₆ H ₄ OMe(<i>p</i>)	2-Amino-5-methylbenzotoluidide.	EtOH	174°	1.50	10.90	10.94
12.	Do	2-Amino-4-(<i>p</i> -chlorophenyl)-thiazole	Me		2-(2-Amino-5-methylbenzamido)-4-(<i>p</i> -chlorophenyl)-thiazole.	Glacial acetic acid	185°	1.20	12.10	12.19
13.	Do	2-Amino-4-phenylthiazole	Me		2-(2-Amino-5-methylbenzamido)-4-phenylthiazole.	EtOH	175°	0.75	13.20	13.55

* From 2 g. of anhydride.

TABLE II

Sulphonamides of the structure

No.	Structure.		Compound synthesised.	Nomenclature.	Method used (A or B) & other conditions of reaction.	Cryst. from.	M.P.	* Yield.		% Nitrogen.	
	R =	R ₁ =						Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
1.	H	H	2-N ⁴ -Acetylsulphanilamidobenzamide.		A; left overnight and ether decanted off. Also R.	50% EtOH	255°	0.70 g.	12.80	12.61	
2.	H	-Ph	2-N ⁴ -Acetylsulphanilamidobenzamide.		A; left over 2 nights. Then refluxed for 3 hours and ether distilled off.	70% AcOH	188°	1.05	10.10	10.27	
3.	H	<i>o</i> -tol.	2-N ⁴ -Acetylsulphanilamidobenz- <i>o</i> -toluidide.		B.	Gl. acetic acid †	195°	0.40	10.00	9.94	
4.	H	<i>m</i> -tol.	2-N ⁴ -Acetylsulphanilamidobenz- <i>m</i> -toluidide.		A; left overnight, refluxed for 3 hours and ether distilled off.	Do	165°	0.67	9.65	9.94	
5.	H	<i>p</i> -tol.	2-N ⁴ -Acetylsulphanilamidobenz- <i>p</i> -toluidide.		A; slightly warmed, left overnight and ether decanted off.	Do	215°	1.18	9.87	9.94	

2-N⁴-Piperidinoacetylsulphanilamidobenzamide.—The condensation between (VIII; R=R¹=H; X=Cl) and piperidine was carried out as above. After distilling off the solvent, the residue was treated with 50 c. c. of water and neutralised with dilute acetic acid. The product was collected and crystallised from 50% ethanol in white needles, m.p. 184°, yield from 2 g. of (VIII) being 1.5 g. (Found: N, 13.20. C₂₀H₂₄O₄N₄S requires N, 13.46 per cent).

2-N⁴-Morpholinoacetylamino-sulphanilamidobenzamide was prepared in the same manner as the above piperidino compound. The product crystallised from dilute ethanol in pale yellow needles, m.p. 188°, yield 0.76 g. from 1 g. of (VIII). (Found: N, 13.40. C₁₉H₂₂O₃N₄S requires N, 13.39 per cent).

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